

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3550673
CZU 81:[008+379.85]

EXTRALINGUISTIC CORRELATION BETWEEN THE CONCEPT OF CULTURE AND TOURISM

Corina Ivaniuc

Free International University of Moldova
52, Vlaicu Pârcalab Str., Chişinău, Republic of Moldova
corina199221@gmail.com

Received: 06.19.2019

Accepted: 09.12.2019

Abstract. This article describes the concept of culture that includes knowledge, traditions, words, abstract norms, religion and other aspects of a nation. Cultural tourism includes alive and artistic forms of human expression referred to as arts along with historical tourism and ethnic tourism. As cultural heritage -tourism is mostly depending on the history, the event in the past has abundant evidence that how the past travels had been changing the entire pages of each century and affected our past life. Unlike our predecessors we can affordably and in a shorter time travel across the world in large numbers comparatively safe. Tourism being one of the biggest and fastest growing industries globally, its benefits and the challenges, are keenly observed by governments affects the economic, socio-cultural, and educational resources of nations.

Keywords: *culture, tourism, cultural tourism, traditions, religious journeys, values.*

Introduction

To define cultural tourism first of all we must determine the meaning of the term *culture*. Anthropologists originally stated that culture and cultures were unique bounded entities with limits and specific characteristics. Cultures were static, they could be captured by anthropological analyses. Their customs, habits, mores, relationships, uniquenesses could all be detailed, and in doing so, and the ways in which each culture was separate from all others could be seen [1].

Culture refers to the cumulative deposit of knowledge, experience, beliefs, values, attitudes, meanings, hierarchies, religion, notions of time, roles, spatial relations, concepts of the universe, and material objects and possessions acquired by a group of people in the course of generations through individual and group striving [2]. The core of a culture is formed by certain values which in terms of tourism will be the basics for the attraction of a given destination. The different levels of culture will be the rituals, the heroes and the symbols of the certain culture which again would serve as a basis for tourism purpose travels [1].

Not aiming to list all the definitions on cultural tourism, it should be necessary to emphasize that the scope of cultural tourism covers those tourism segments that could not be classified as the elements of mass and passive tourism [3]. The classic attractions of cultural tourism can be classified into three groups:

- built and material values (buildings, material values of different art forms);
- cultural values connected to everyday life (free time, leisure, lifestyle, habits, gastronomy);
- events and festivals;

The cultural heritage of any nation is represented not only by the works of artists, architects, musicians, writers, works of scientists, but it is also intangible heritage, including folklore, crafts, festivals, religious rituals, traditions, gastronomy etc.

Religious travelling, particularly pilgrimages make a part of cultural tourism. For example, we can refer here to thousands of Catholics around the world who want to visit the Vatican and other holy places, Jews travel to Israel, the Holocaust memorial sites and Mecca is the main destination for Muslims around the world [4].

Relationship analysis between the concept of culture and tourism

One of the strongest people motivations for the trip is a cultural expression of the other people and other nations. Cultural features of different regions of the world are increasingly encouraging people to take holidays and free time traveling. The development of cultural elements of the region is a means of increasing resources to attract tourist flows. The development of tourism depends on the uniqueness of cultural patrimony. The level of cultural development can be used to create a favorable image of tourism trends in the market. Thus tourism is an important tool for promoting cultural ties and international cooperation. In many countries, tourism may be included in the so-called policy of cultural relations [3].

The emergence of cultural tourism in research as the object of study has its origins in the early twentieth century, but only in 2002 the International Council on Cultural and Historical Monuments published a formal definition as follows: Cultural and cultural tourism - cognitive is that form of tourism which focuses on the cultural environment and that in turn includes cultural and historic landmarks or cultural heritage and historical values and lifestyle of the local people, arts, crafts, traditions and customs of the local population [5].

In order to explain the concept of cultural tourism we need to connect the two terms: culture and tourism. They have many elements in common. If, for this purpose, we consider only man made values in tourism, and if we leave aside for the moment natural values, the common areas of culture and tourism are the spaces and phenomena that people have been shaping, which reflect human creativity and interest [8].

What is essentially different is the place of action. People can participate in culture everywhere, in all spaces, while tourism has its defined areas, outside the visitor's place of residence. The presence of natural beauty and richness, high-quality communication connections, an adequate supply of accommodation and food, make cultural heritage become a product which attracts users. What tourists take home is an echo in their experience, or its sophisticated expression shown in books, souvenirs or the virtual world of heritage on CDs and DVDs [3].

Marketing in culture is philosophy, the knowledge and art of pointing to the values attractive to individuals or groups. The function of marketing is to make potential tourists perceive these values and use them, at the same time bringing material benefits and helping develop cultural activities in specific environments. In a sense, this is the art of identifying values and using them in contemporary life. Through the modern promotion of the values of cultural heritage, interest in a certain environment is created, as is the wish to learn more about a certain culture and interest to visit the location. All these can bring market results,

primarily in the field of tourism, an economic branch which uses the cultural heritage of a country as a stimulus to characterize and emphasize a place as a tourism destination [3].

Conceptual definitions are concerned with the nature of the cultural tourism phenomenon, and in particular tend to concentrate on what motivates the tourist to visit cultural attractions. In order to try and clarify the meaning of cultural tourism, a conceptual definition was proposed based on the way in which tourists' consume culture. According to Mary Ann Littrell, culture can be viewed as comprising what people think (attitudes, beliefs, ideas and values), what people do (normative behavior patterns or way of life) and what people make (artworks, artefacts, cultural products). Culture is therefore composed of processes (the ideas and way of life of people) and the products of those processes (buildings, artefacts, art, customs, 'atmosphere') [7].

Looking at culture in this way, cultural tourism is not just about visiting sites and monuments, which has tended to be the 'traditional' view of cultural tourism, but it also involves consuming the way of life of the areas visited. Both of these activities involve the collection of new knowledge and experiences. The conceptual definition proposed by Greg Richards is: the movement of persons to cultural attractions away from their normal place of residence, with the intention to gather new information and experiences to satisfy their cultural needs [4].

Cultural tourism is defined by the World Tourism Organization as trips, whose main or concomitant goal is visiting the sights and events whose cultural and historical value has turned them being a part of the cultural heritage of a community [8]. An important feature of cultural tourism according to this definition is the assumption that visiting cultural and historical sites and events, related to cultural heritage is not necessarily the main motive for the trip. In this context cultural-historical tourism is rarely implemented in a "clean" look and most often is combined with other traditional and specialized types of tourism. This substantial feature reveals opportunities to improve the effectiveness of national and regional tourism through the development of cultural-historical tourism - through absorption and integration of cultural-historical resources in the regional tourism product and development on this basis of a regional tourism brand.

The key category in that definition is the concept of cultural heritage which includes intangible and tangible movable and immovable heritage as a set of cultural values that are carriers of historical memory, national identity and have scientific or cultural value. The function of cultural tourism is an instrument for economic development that achieves economic growth by attracting visitors outside the community-host who are motivated generally or partially by an interest in the historical, artistic, scientific or related to lifestyle and traditions reality and facts of a community, region, group or institution. Such a travel is focused on the feeling of cultural environment, including landscapes, visual and performing arts, lifestyles, values, traditions and events.

Tourism is looking for ways to create marketable tourism products as well as environment for work and life. Cultural-cognitive tourism is an interaction between cultural, ethnic and historical components of the society or of the place to be used as resources to attract tourists and tourism development.

Modern cultural tourism is an apparent paradox. It is a form of tourism that has become so popular that everybody seems familiar with it and many people are keen to develop it. But our understanding of the concept has not kept pace with its growth. The concept of cultural tourism is still fairly vague, and many different definitions of term are in circulation. Part of

the problem lies in the fact that culture is itself so difficult to define, but the different approaches to cultural tourism have tended to add to the confusion. Different definitions have been developed for different purposes, whether to understand measure or identify cultural tourism [7].

Tourism is a specific socio-economic phenomenon of modern civilization, rooted in the life of society, and influenced by its evolution. Cultural tourism is a tool for economic development, leading to economic growth by attracting visitors from outside the host community and are partially or generally motivated by an interest in the components of historical, artistic, scientific or related to lifestyle realities, traditions and information to a community, region, group or institution.

Tourism is a global force for economic and regional development. Tourism development brings with it a mix of benefits and costs and the growing field of tourism economics is making an important contribution to tourism policy, planning and business practices [3].

Tourism activity provides the development of poorer areas, the realization of tourist facilities, work for native population, thus creating conditions for better living (an example being rural or cultural tourism, which is not focus necessarily on comfort and leisure, but natural landscaper, traditions, folklore, customs.

In the XXIst century the tourism global market creates an organic and interdependent system in which the supply and demand side experiences significant changes both in time and space and also from the perspectives of the quantitative and qualitative aspects or components. Newer and newer regions and tourism products will be involved in the international and domestic tourism trends as well and in the ever growing competition only such a tourism destination of tourism actor can survive which or who can provide an ever growing standard of quality [7].

Greg Richards states that culture and tourism were two of the major growth industries of the 20th century, and towards the end of the century the combination of these two sectors into 'cultural tourism' had become one of the most desirable development options for countries and regions around the world [5].

Tourism plays an important role in the economy and the fact that creates new jobs work, having thus a major contributor to attract surplus labor from other sectors and thus reduce unemployment. Tourism can be considered as the most dynamic sector, through the creation of jobs in various forms that led to the setting of the following types of employment:

- direct employment - people working in a tourism company, including hotels, restaurants, tourist shops, travel agents, tour operators;
- Indirect employment - jobs in the sectors supply products in food commodities and nonfood products respectively industry, agriculture, fisheries;
- employment in the construction sector - jobs in infrastructure construction they usually are temporary, but may take longer in areas where there is a continuous development of tourism.

Tourism is the activity that has permanently and rapidly developed during time, knowing a variety of types and forms. In the urban and in the rural environment, cultural tourism can attract a significant number of tourists. Keeping the cultural identity of a place, under the conditions of globalization and the tourist valorization of the cultural heritage are the main elements that can lead to the development of cultural tourism [4].

At the European level cultural tourism is very much appreciated by tourists, promoted and supported by numerous organizations and through specific policies.

Economic impacts of cultural tourism

The tourism industry generates substantial economic benefits to both host countries and tourists' home countries. Especially in developing countries, one of the primary motivations for a region to promote itself as a tourism destination is the expected economic improvement.

Tourism's role in the economy is often perceived as being limited to the hospitality industry (cafes, hotels and restaurants) and outbound and inbound travel agencies and carriers, which form the leading service sector in many countries. However, the economic impact of tourism is much greater, since many inputs are needed in order to produce tourism and leisure services, spanning the whole range of farm, agro food and industrial production, including the production of capital goods as well as construction and public works [3].

Cultural tourism attracts a growing number of tourists. According to the European Commission survey, 20% of visits in Europe have cultural motivation, while 60% of the European tourists are interested in discovering culture during their trip. Since that historic attractions are mainly in cities, cultural tourism is naturally associated with urban tourism. Competitive investment in cultural facilities and infrastructure needed to host tourists from urban areas having a direct impact on the economy and inducing an improvement in living standards. Spatial organization of cultural resources in the city and their relationships with infrastructure (hotels, transportation, shopping areas) is important for the successful development of cultural tourism strategy.

The cultural sector of the city includes:

- physical characteristics of the city and cultural heritage;
- cultural facilities in the broadest sense, including events, exhibitions, institutions and infrastructure such as theaters, museums, galleries, libraries, recreational facilities and sale of art.

Tourism has a variety of economic impacts. Tourists contribute to sales, profits, jobs, tax revenues, and income in an area. The most direct effects occur within the primary tourism sectors -lodging, restaurants, transportation, amusements, and retail trade. By its secondary effects tourism affects most sectors of the economy. An economic impact analysis of tourism activity normally focuses on changes in sales, income, and employment in a region resulting from tourism activity [6].

Economic impacts of cultural tourism are very hard to assess because there is no system of indicators through which data would become available and simple to measure. Except for this reason, there is the aggravating circumstance that cultural tourism is a complex phenomenon because it is tightly connected with other economic branches which benefit from development of cultural tourism and the assessment of the economic benefits of cultural tourism is often lower since it is hard to estimate the impact of cultural tourism on other branches, which increases the economic impact of cultural tourism [1].

The economic impact of cultural tourism can be analyzed from the two main viewpoints which include macroeconomic and microeconomic level. On the microeconomic level, the economic value of cultural tourism may be defined as a group of benefits for a certain society. Economic value of cultural tourism on the macroeconomic level is reflected in the stimulation of other economic branches through direct, indirect, and induced effects. Therefore, it is fair to say that cultural tourism is a method of development, because development of cultural

tourism stimulates development of individual economic branches, which contributes to total development of a certain destination [7].

Monitoring and identification of the economic effect of cultural tourism is necessary because, by forming a cultural tourism product, non-economic resources are transformed into economic, which results in the realization of economic effects. Economic effects need to be identified in order to assess the impact of cultural tourism, which is a basis for strategic plans with the objective to maximize economic effects by valorization of cultural resources [4].

In general, economic impacts of cultural tourism are direct, indirect, and induced.

Direct effects are reflected in economic benefits of individual cultural tourism offer holders which realize benefits by selling cultural tourism products. Indirect effects are benefits realized by other tourism holders in which cultural tourists realize consumption. Induced effects occur as a result of direct and indirect effects, and they are reflected in increased consumption of the tourism holders thanks to the economic benefit achieved by selling their own products. The total economic effect, in fact, represents a sum of direct, indirect, and induced effects.

Indirect effects can sometimes be much larger than direct effects when it comes to certain cultural tourism products, for example, events. Therefore, depending on cultural products in a certain destination, it may occur that direct effects of economic tourism are smaller than the indirect effects, because of which it is important to consider total effects of cultural tourism. This is also very hard, because, unlike indirect effects, direct effects are more simple to establish, measure and monitor [9].

Conclusions

Tourism not only directly affects the quality of life but also indirectly through its interference with some sectors (agriculture, industry, trade). Thus, tourism is provided an outlet for surplus of labor force, capitalize the higher local products operated jointly with other sectors (industry, agriculture) forms of unconventional energy, stimulate some industries which are producing consumer goods with the role to improve the quality of life, contribute to the development of competition, which leads to improving quality standards by some industries.

In conclusion, the tourism product is the result of work carried out by various economic agents, tourism acting as a stimulator of the global economic system. Tourism development engages many components with the stimulant and training effects as both the tourist industry and other branch of activity participate directly or indirectly in the economic growth process.

References

1. What is Culture? [online]. [Accessed 10.03.2019]. Available at: <https://www.sccs.swarthmore.edu/users/00/ckenned1/culture.html>
2. Culture [online]. [Accessed 15.02.2019]. Available at: <https://www.tamu.edu/faculty/choudhury/culture.html>
3. Brida J. G. The Economic Impacts of Cultural Tourism. In: The Routledge Handbook of Cultural Tourism. New York: Routledge, 2013, pp. 110–115.
4. Richards G. Cultural Tourism in Europe. Wallingford: CAB International, 1996.
5. Nature and Characteristics of Cultural Tourism [online]. [Accessed 10.02.2019]. Available at: <http://www.montana-vidin-dolj.com/en/publications/?NewsId=3>

6. Robinson S. Cultural Tourism in a Changing World [online]. [Accessed 01.03.2019]. Available at: <http://www00.unibg.it/dati/corsi/44108/50648-smith-robinson-proofs.pdf>
7. Littrell M. A. Shopping Experiences and Marketing of Culture to Tourists. In: *Tourism and Culture: Image, Identity and Marketing*. Centre for Travel and Tourism: University of Northumbria, 1997, pp.107-120
8. World Trade Report [online]. [Accessed 06.03.2019]. Available at: https://www.wto.org/english/res_e/booksp_e/anrep_e/world_trade_report12_e.pdf
9. Aitchison, C. Theorizing Other Discourses of Tourism, Gender and Culture. In: *Tourist Studies*, vol. 1, 2001, pp. 133-147.